

Synthesis of 3-(5-Methyl-3-isoxazolyl)-2-styrylquinazolin-4-(3H)-ones and their Antifungal Activity

S. SAILAJA, E. THIRMAL RAO, E. RAJANARENDAR and A. KRISHNAMURTHY*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 18 March 1987, revised 9 September 1987, accepted 30 December 1987

3-(5-Methyl-3-isoxazolyl)-2-styrylquinazolin-4-(3H)-ones (3) have been prepared by the interaction of isoxazole Schiff bases (2) with 2-methyl-3,1-benzoxazine-4-one (1). The structure of the compounds (3) have been established by their elemental analysis and ir, pmr and mass spectral data. The products have been also prepared through an unambiguous route. Antifungal activity of the compounds has been studied.

METHYL substituted five- and six-membered oxygen heterocycles have been converted into nitrogen analogues bearing styryl group on treatment with Schiff bases^{1,2}. In this transformation, so far, heterocyclic anils have not been used. As a part of comprehensive investigation on isoxazoles from our laboratories, the isoxazole anils have been used as synthons in the present investigation for converting oxygen heterocycles into their nitrogen analogues. Moreover, isoxazolyl quinazolones, hitherto unknown, may show wide range physiological activities because the two heterocycles are known to be biologically important³⁻⁹.

The Schiff bases, 3-benzalamino-5-methylisoxazoles (2)¹⁰ were prepared in good yields (70-90%) by the condensation of 3-amino-5-methylisoxazoles with aromatic aldehydes in boiling alcohol. 2-Methyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (1) was obtained by the cyclisation of anthranilic acid with acetic anhydride¹¹. The reaction of the benzoxazinone (1) with isoxazole anils was carried out by refluxing in glacial acetic acid in the presence of sodium acetate for 3 h (Scheme 1). Some of the products

Scheme 1

were separated from the clear reaction mixture on cooling, whereas the others precipitated on diluting the reaction mixture with water. The products (30-70%) were characterised as 3-(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)-2-styrylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones on the basis of elemental analysis and ir, pmr and mass spectral

data. The mechanism of the transformation involves the Michael addition of the benzoxazinone methyl group to the azomethine moiety, the ring opening of the oxazine nucleus and recyclicalisation to the pyrimidine ring¹.

The ir spectra of 3 showed peaks at 1 680 (imide C=O) and 970 cm⁻¹ (-CH=CH- bend). The ¹H nmr spectra showed two singlets with fine structure at δ 2.58 and 6.25 assignable to isoxazole methyl and isoxazole ring proton, respectively. The fine structure is due to allylic coupling present between them. One of the double bond protons (β-hydrogen) appeared as doublet at δ 6.6 (J 16 Hz). The α-hydrogen was found along with aromatic multiplet because of the deshielding influence of the two quinazolinone nitrogens. The mass spectra showed molecular ion peaks at *m/z* 329 (67%) (Chart 1).

Chart 1

The base peak appeared at *m/z* 286. In the molecular ion the isoxazole ring undergoes skeletal transformation to give azirine (A) which optionally loses ketone or acetyl group leading to the ions (B) and (C), respectively. This fragmentation is the characteristic feature of isoxazole nucleus whose N-O bond is extremely weak¹². The characteristic cleavage of quinazolinone is revealed by the appearance of the benzazirine ion (D) at *m/z* 90.

The compounds 3 were further confirmed by unambiguous synthesis starting from benzoxazinone.

The benzoxazinone (1) on treatment with 3-amino-5-methylisoxazole in acetic acid gave 2-methyl-3-(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (4). 4 on heating with benzaldehyde in isopropanol for 6 h yielded a product identical with 3 in all aspects, i.e. m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra.

Antifungal activity: The antifungal activity of isoxazolylquinazolinones was evaluated by the cup-plate method¹⁸. *Paecilomyces varioti* was used as the test organism. Appreciable activity was exhibited by unsubstituted compound and feeble activity was shown by *p*-chloro and α -thienyl compounds. Rest of the compounds were inactive.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked on tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were run on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, the nmr spectra (100 MHz) on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and the mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument at 70 eV.

3-(5-Methyl-3-isoxazolyl)-2-styrylquinazolin-4-(3H)-ones (3): A mixture of benzoxazinone (0.01 mol) and isoxazole Schiff's base (0.01 mol) was refluxed in acetic acid (AnalaR) with sodium acetate for 3 h. The solid separated from the resulting solution on cooling, was filtered and recrystallised from benzene-ethyl acetate. In some cases, where the solid did not separate, the reaction mixture was diluted and processed to yield the solid product (Table 1);

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF ISOXAZOLYL QUINAZOLIN-4(3H)-ONES (3)*

Compd. no.	Ar	Yield		Mol. formulae
		%	M.p. °C	
3a	Phenyl	60	195	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃
3b	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	55	178	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃
3c	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	50	180	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃
3d	3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl	45	174	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄
3e	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	30	187	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₄
3f	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	65	198	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ Cl
3g	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	70	194	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ Cl
3h	Salicylyl	30	160	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃
3i	5-Chlorosalicylyl	35	215	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ Cl
3j	3,5-Dichlorosalicylyl	40	220	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂
3k	3,5-Dibromosalicylyl	35	226	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₃ Br ₂
3l	α -Thienyl	60	175	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃ S

* C, H and N analyses found satisfactory.

** Solvent of crystallisation: benzene-ethyl acetate.

$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1680 (N-CO) and 970 cm⁻¹ (CH=CH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.2 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 6.6 (1H, d, =CH- β) and 7.2-8.3 (10H, m, ArH and =CH- α).

2-Methyl-3(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (4): A mixture of benzoxazinone (0.01 mol) and 3-amino-5-methylisoxazole (0.01 mol) was refluxed in acetic acid (AnalaR) for 3 h. The product separated on cooling was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 165° (Found: C, 77.5; H, 2.60; N, 10.69. C₁₈H₁₁N₃O₃ requires: C, 77.6; H, 2.64; N, 10.7%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1685 (NCO); δ (CDCl₃) 2.6 (3H, s, isoxazole-CH₃), 6.4 (1H, s, isoxazole-H), 2.3 (3H, s, quinazolinone-CH₃) and 7.0-8.1 (4H, m, ArH).

Styrylation of 4: A mixture of 4 (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was refluxed in isopropanol for 6 h. The solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from benzene-ethyl acetate to give 3.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. E. V. Sundaram, Head, Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal, for facilities. Two of the authors (S.S. and E.T.R.) are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. A. K. MUKERJEE and P. KUMAR, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1980, 24, 936.
2. S. REDDY, P. HANUMANTHU and C. V. RATNAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 646.
3. R. P. BUEH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2344.
4. A. RANDALL and M. BAGDON, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1959, 80, 626.
5. L. R. KOLOMOISTEV, M. A. ALFEREVA, N. I. MATVIENKO and A. K. SHIENKMAN, *Mikrobiol. Zh.*, 1967, 29, 342.
6. P. B. REDDY, S. M. REDDY, E. RAJANARENDAR and A. K. MURTHY, *Indian Phytopathol.*, 1984, 37, 969.
7. S. K. SAXENA and S. SOMASHEKARA, *J. Indian Med. Res.*, 1972, 60, 284.
8. L. H. MILTON and H. ANN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 971.
9. K. L. REDDY, P. B. REDDY, S. M. REDDY and P. LINGAIAH, *Indian Phytopathol.*, 1985, 38, 861.
10. S. SAILAJA, E. RAJANARENDAR, C. J. RAO and A. K. MURTHY, *Sulfur Lett.*, 1987, 6, 81.
11. T. MARSTON and A. K. HARVEY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 529.
12. M. OHASHI, H. KAMACHI, H. KAKISAWA, A. TATEMATSU, H. YOSHIZUMI and H. NAKATA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, 3, 379.
13. D. C. GROVER and W. A. RANDALL, "Assay Methods of Antibiotics Laboratory Manual", Medical Encyclopedia, New York, 1955, p. 26.